

Deliverable D8.2

Integration of genomics and phenotypic data

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1. Executive Summary

The Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project aims to overcome or lower barriers in clinical diagnostics, treatment as well as secondary use (e.g. research) by facilitating access to fragmented (i.e. fragmentation caused by 1) geographical and institutional islands, 2) technical incompatibility, 3) legal and regulatory divergence, and 4) semantic barriers (different languages and different coding standards) human genomics data across Europe. The project establishes a federated, secure infrastructure, but faces interoperability challenges towards the refined eHealth European Interoperability Framework¹ due to the diversity of implementations of law and regulations, various organisational setups, data sources and infrastructures.

Establishing harmonised minimal data models (i.e. a blueprint that shows how data is organized and connected) and specifications within GDI facilitates seamless data exchange, supporting better collaboration in healthcare and contributing to improved patient care. Deliverable 8.2 encapsulates the collaborative efforts of GDI, 1+MG, Genome of Europe, B1MG(plus) and ERDERA initiatives towards establishing harmonised minimal data models and specifications for genomic data exchange and integration.

Efforts focused on leveraging prior work from 1+MG and B1MG initiatives to define minimal datasets for GDI use cases, particularly in Cancer, Infectious Diseases, Rare Diseases and the Genome of Europe. The main drivers for the work described in this deliverable are Genome of Europe (GDI T7.1 and 1+MG WG10), Cancer (GDI T7.4 and 1+MG WG9), Infectious diseases (GDI T7.3 and 1+MG WG11), and Rare disease (GDI T7.2 and 1+MG WG8) as well as the framework for solving interoperability scenarios described in D8.7 supporting us in developing and harmonising the minimal data model. Collaborative refinement processes ensured comprehensive adherence to the agreed upon data model and specifications.

Substantial progress has been made, including the successful delivery of v1.0 of the 1+MG Harmonised Minimal Data model (HMD). The work continues towards next version(s) of the HMD v1.x/v2.x that will include 1) the current advancements in finalizing the minimal dataset for Infectious Diseases, 2) the onboarding of the new 1+MG WG12 use case on pharmacogenomics, 3) the work on onboarding the datasets needed to run the first use case (the Allele Frequency browser) with real data from Genome of Europe, and 4) cross-walks between various internationally mature terminology standards like SNOMED CT, LOINC, ICD-10 for both the concepts and values of the HMD following the SSSOM (Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings) method². This deliverable also describes the first results of implementing (as in mapping) the HMD v1.0 into Beacon v2.

¹ [Refinement of the eHealth European Interoperability Framework \(ReEIF\)](#)

² SSSOM: <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

Challenges such as accommodating diverse dataset standards, like the upcoming HealthDCAT-AP standard designed specifically for the HealthData@EU infrastructure and clarifying basic data standards within GDI require ongoing dialogue and collaboration.

Lastly, standardisation, interoperability, and collaborative frameworks are a priority in GDI and efforts towards this goal will continue.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>Yes (interoperability enables linkage of genomic data)</p>
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	<p>Yes (interoperable clinical/phenotypic data can be linked and analysed)</p>
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 5</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes (better sustainable operation by defining what metadata needs capturing, and building and supporting a community of experts to define, implement, use and manage the HMD)</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Introduction

3.1. Background

The partners in the '1+ Million Genomes' (1+MG) initiative and its implementation project European Genomic Data Infrastructure³ (GDI) and the genomic sequencing project Genome of Europe⁴ (GoE) aim to enable secure access to genomics and the corresponding clinical data across Europe for better research, personalised healthcare and health policy making. In addition, they participate in many other (inter)national projects that also aim to improve disease prevention, allow for more personalised treatments and support groundbreaking research. Obviously, there is a great deal of potential synergy across all of these projects. To unlock this potential, WP8, specifically task 8.2, invests in interoperability for joint discovery, queries and analyses within GDI and related projects that are part of 1+MG and GDI working groups, supported by and in alignment with the European Health Data Space⁵ (EHDS) and key EU-funded projects like GDI, TEHDAS⁶, HealthData@EU⁷ and ERDERA⁸.

3.2. Objective

Aim of this deliverable is to report on the mechanisms contributing towards the development and harmonisation of the minimal data models needed within the WP7 use cases, resulting in the semantic interoperability of genomic and phenotypic and clinical information, including standards, systems and recommendations for adoption within 1+MG, its implementation projects GDI and Genome of Europe as well as projects specifically linked to one of the 1+MG use case WGs, like ERDERA for rare diseases.

3.3. Outline

This deliverable starts with outlining the process and methods used to develop the HMD v1.0. It then details the collaborative work carried out with all involved, including the publication, presentation and documentation of results. Finally, it describes the initial steps towards inclusion of real data from Genome of Europe within the GDI infrastructure, enabling Genome of Europe to execute its first use case, an Allele Frequency Browser. This effort simultaneously contributed to the maximal attainable product defined within the GDI project with the goal of moving into production by April 2025.

³ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

⁴ <https://genomeofeurope.eu/>

⁵

https://health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en

⁶ <https://tehdas.eu/>

⁷ <https://acceptance.data.health.europa.eu/?locale=en>

⁸ <https://erdera.org/>

4. Methods

The work described in this deliverable leverages prior work from 1+MG and B1MG⁹ & B1MGPlus¹⁰ initiatives on the phenotypic and clinical metadata framework¹¹. This B1MG framework describes, in a commonly understandable language, the principles, models, and recommendations for sharing and linking of phenotypic and clinical metadata and genetic metadata between the member states. It provides guidance on which standards, terminologies, and tools to use.

Succeeding this B1MG framework, GDI has published D8.7¹², a framework for solving interoperability scenarios. Our deliverable applies the interoperability building blocks (e.g. building block HealthDCAT-AP¹³) from D8.7 on interoperability scenarios to delineate different interoperability scenarios in GDI. The interoperability building blocks are essential for storing, organising and manipulating data so that it can be accessed and manipulated efficiently, as well as used in algorithms and applications. They are the drivers for interoperability within the 1+MG initiative, its mission related projects GDI and Genome of Europe, as well as projects that are related to one of the 1+MG use case WG like WG8 on rare diseases that closely aligns with the recently started ERDERA project.

This deliverable describes the work accomplished towards the publication of the 1+MG Harmonised minimal data model (1+MG HMD) v1.0, its successor and future versions..

4.1. Related work

This work is connected to the following GDI work packages and deliverables:

- Pillar 3, WP7, GDI use cases:
 - Genome of Europe (GDI T7.1 and 1+MG WG10)
 - Rare disease (GDI T7.2 and 1+MG WG8)
 - Infectious diseases (GDI T7.3 and 1+MG WG11)
 - Cancer (GDI T7.4 and 1+MG WG9)
- Pillar 3, GDI Milestone MS26: Initial set of questions by the use cases
- Pillar 3, WP8, D8.7: Report on semantic interoperability scenarios

The three listed works are main drivers for the work described and all three supported us in developing and harmonising the minimal data model for 1+MG.

The work described in this deliverable served as input and/or contribution to the development and deployment of:

⁹ <https://b1mg-project.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://b1mgplus.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/10058688>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11550315>

¹³ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-5/>

- Pillar 2, WP3, MS7: Early adopter production nodes deployed with synthetic real-like data.
- Pillar 2, WP3, MS8: Incremental demonstrator
- Pillar 2, WP4, D4.3: User portal live cataloguing data within the GDI.
- Pillar 2, WP4, MS11: Development of the user portal deployed.
- Pillar 2, WP4, MS12: Production user portal deployed, with discoverability and data access functionality
- Collaborative work of GDI & Genome of Europe in development and deployment of the Allele Frequency browser on real Genome of Europe datasets.

The following user communities and groups have contributed to and/or will be continuing progressing, implementing and using the results:

- The 1+MG initiative working groups:
 - 1+MG WG3: Common standards and minimal dataset for clinical and phenotypic data
 - 1+MG WG4: Good sequencing practice
 - 1+MG WG8: use case Rare diseases
 - 1+MG WG9: use case Cancer
 - 1+MG WG10: use case Population Genomics (Common and complex diseases / Genome of Europe)
 - 1+MG WG11: use case Infectious diseases
 - 1+MG WG12: use case Pharmacogenomics
- The Genome of Europe project (various workpackages)
- ERDERA (extending RD3¹⁴)
- CANDLE
- UNCAN-CONNECT

4.2. The road towards the 1+MG HMD v1.0

The road towards publication of the first version of the 1+MG HMD (v1.0) in February 2025 as part of the GDI February Feature Freeze started at the end of 2022 with the results available from B1MG. Since B1MG and GDI in part overlap, the results obtained in B1MG (as at the end of B1MG published at "The 1+MG Framework Recommendations for Data models, standards & ontologies"¹⁵) were the starting point for GDI task 8.2. The processes started in B1MG (monthly teleconferences (TC) with the 1+MG WG3 experts) were optimised over time such that a dedicated small team of data and domain experts (called the 1+MG HMD-team) prepared in small steps (a kind of agile process) the next review of (parts of) the 1+MG HMD for the upcoming TC as well as processed all comments/input/amendments as results from the previous TC to be presented for final check and if deemed okay for approval to be

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giae058>

¹⁵ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/data-models-ontologies>

fixed/frozen. Step by step this resulted in the official release of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 in February 2025.

The 1+MG HMD adheres to the sunflower concept as described in the earlier mentioned framework¹⁶. The sunflower initially consists of the minimal data models as defined by each of the 1+MG use cases: WG8 Rare diseases, WG9 Cancer, WG10 use case Population Genomics (Common and complex diseases / Genome of Europe), and WG11 Infectious diseases (at the start of GDI, due to COVID, it started with COVID; mid 2025 it was extended to more generic infectious diseases)).

Figure 1: The four individual sunflower petals for each of the initial 1+MG use cases. The petal of Genome of Europe is smaller because of the limited amount of concepts needed at the conception of Genome of Europe. The petal of the Infectious Diseases is colored with a paler yellow colour because it at that time only was based on the COVID use case.

Each of the data models belonging to a use case can be seen as a petal of the sunflower (see Figure 1). Where the petals overlap (as in share the same concepts) the petals form the core of the sunflower (“the harmonised part”). Where the petals differ, those petal parts remain petals in the sunflower (the protruding petal parts of a sunflower).

¹⁶ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/data-models-ontologies>

Figure 2: The four individual sunflower petals in part overlap and form the core of the sunflower. This is just a visualisation used to explain the concept at the start of GDI and the actual overlapping part within the 1+MG harmonised minimal data model is much bigger (as in the core of the sunflower)

The 1+MG harmonised minimal data model also differentiates between mandatory, recommended, optional and conditional elements. The “**minimal**” part in the name “1+MG harmonised **minimal** data model” refers to the fact that a dataset that conforms to the 1+MG HMD at least **must** contain all the mandatory concepts (where the other concepts can be included but could also be left empty (i.e. omitted)).

4.3. Cross-walks between internationally mature standards following SSSOM

Semantic unification ensures that health and medical concepts are defined clearly and without ambiguity, so both primary users—such as medical specialists—and secondary users interpret exchanged information in the same way. By harmonising and standardising coded healthcare data, organisations strengthen the safety and effectiveness of care and enable reliable secondary use for service delivery, research, and management. This preserves the full meaning of the data so that what is originally captured and used is exactly the same and understood when re-used.

Since multiple mature international standards are in use the 1+MG WG3 for both the data item as well as the values have defined the preferred standard to be used. Preferred terminologies under the EHDS will be defined later in 2026 (following Xt-EHR¹⁷ use case specifications) and this will provide future directions to be incorporated on national and international level. To accommodate the use of multiple international mature standards, like SNOMED¹⁸ CT, LOINC¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://www.xt-ehr.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://www.snomed.org/>

¹⁹ <https://loinc.org/>

and ICD-10²⁰, we initiated the work on cross-walks between various internationally mature standards both the data items and values of the HMD following the SSSOM (Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings) method²¹. For registered users SNOMED international already provides access to maintained mappings to SNOMED CT²². The same SSSOM method has been applied in multiple workshops working on the implementation of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 into Beacon²³ v2 (initial work focused on comparing both data models and identifying matches, as well as identifying gaps for which the 1+MG HMD v1.0 did not have any match at all.

Since enforcing and working with one single terminology at this moment is not realistic given expected costs, varying terminology implementations amongst many EHRs and alike as well as choices enforced by national memberstate policies these cross-walks as part of the 1+MG HMD for now are the (only) pragmatic way forward. However, current and future developments in Artificial Intelligence and specifically Large Language Models (LLMs) based on the work we and others have done, might help creating or supporting these cross-walks by automated mappings by these LLMs.

4.4. HealthDCAT-AP for 1+MG dataset description

So where the 1+MG HMD specifies the concepts within a dataset or database (i.e. a data dictionary or the data codebook), GDI also needs a dataset description, also known as metadata about a (in this case 1+MG) dataset. Task 8.2 initially created a specific "model for submission of descriptive metadata" containing all mandatory, recommended, and optional fields needed to uptake and list a dataset in the GDI dataset catalogue as designed and developed by GDI WP4 (the catalogue is an integral part of the GDI User Portal²⁴). Based on the European developments of DCAT-AP²⁵ and since 2023 the development of HealthDCAT-AP by the EHDS2 Pilot, and the uptake and hand-over of the HealthDCAT-AP within the development of the central services of HealthData@EU since mid 2025²⁶, we, as task 8.2 together with the metadata squad of Pillar II, decided that we will deprecate (i.e. remove it from the 1+MG HMD) the "model for submission of descriptive metadata" and replace it by the HealthDCAT-AP as currently being implemented and tested by HealthData@EU. This resulted in publication of a minor release v1.1 of the 1+MG HMD in December 2025.

²⁰ <https://icd.who.int/browse10/2019/en>

²¹ SSSOM: <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

²² mappings maintained by SNOMED int are published on <https://mlds.ihtsdotools.org/#/login>

²³ <https://genomebeacons.org/>

²⁴ <https://portal.gdi.lu/>

²⁵ <https://semiceu.github.io/DCAT-AP/releases/3.0.1/>

²⁶ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-5/>

4.5. Governance and quality control of the 1+MG HMD and datasets

As already laid out in the 1+MG phenotypic and clinical metadata framework²⁷ there is a need for governance and quality control of standards. Where most of the mature (inter)national standards are maintained and governed on their own, there is a need to:

- ensure that different standards (like HL7²⁸ and FHIR²⁹; SNOMED CT and ICD; OMOP CDM³⁰ and openEHR³¹) **work together** rather than in isolation
- define **specific roles** (e.g., standard owner, developer, end-user) to ensure someone is always responsible for keeping a standard up to date
- emphasize that standards should be developed based on **actual use cases**

An international standard (i.e. ISO or alike) to address all those aspects in an integrated approach as far as we know does not yet exist. However, as 1+MG/GDI we could leverage the Dutch based NEN 7522³², which focuses on the governance and management of the standards themselves as well as ensuring that they work together rather than in isolation.

Based on the NEN 7522 as a start GDI and the future EDIC should:

- Produce a (bi)yearly delta of the 1+MG HMD
- Perform a (bi)yearly check on the created mappings against the official mappings
- Perform a (bi)yearly check on deprecated items

The framework for data governance (also the future EDIC) is being described in deliverable 2.4³³ of GDI in which parts cover the above mentioned aspects.

5. Description of work accomplished

The infrastructure envisioned by GDI to support the 1+MG ambition aims to support data discovery from a centralised User Portal, which facilitates sensitive (i.e. genomic and phenotypic) data access federated across each participating country, so the sensitive data does not need to leave the country of origin. The data discovery functionality is supported by the use of one or more genomic Beacons supporting individual level queries, an Allele Frequency Beacon supporting allele frequency queries for pre-defined cohorts, and a Fair Data Point³⁴ (FDP) each of which is deployed in each country. A research user can utilise the User Portal to query the dataset metadata via the FDP, cohort allele frequencies via the Allele Frequency Beacons, and limited phenotypic and genomic data via the

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/10058688>

²⁸ <https://www.hl7.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.fhir.org/>

³⁰ <https://ohdsi.github.io/CommonDataModel/>

³¹ <https://openehr.org/>

³² <https://www.nen.nl/en/nen-7522-2021-en-324054>

³³ [W 202506 - GDI_D2.4 Framework for data governance_FV.docx](#)

³⁴ <https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>

Beacons. This way the User Portal either distributes a Beacon query to either type of Beacon, or 'harvests' the dataset metadata from the FDP, each of which support the HealthDCAT-AP requirements as described above.

Within the data journey as depicted by Pillar II & III next to the "real data" various types of metadata are being used. First of all the descriptive metadata about a dataset is harvested by the GDI User Portal (i.e. the catalogue) such that the dataset can be found and searched for. Next is the ELSI related metadata of a dataset, like license and access rights. Also metadata that handles the provenance of the dataset (e.g. which version of a certain pipeline was used to create a certain sequencing result, and a ledger recording transactions, events or state changes that occur as data moves through our data journey) and last but not least the 1+MG Harmonised Minimal Datamodel that outlines the structure, content, and meaning of each variable and (coded) values in a dataset (for this aspect we will use the term 1+MG HMD). For each of them the work done will be described in the sections to follow.

5.1. The 1+MG Harmonised Minimal Datamodel

As a starting point for working on this deliverable, we used the achieved status quo of the 1+MG minimal phenotypic datasets of cancer, rare disease, infectious disease and common and complex diseases/GoE as discussed and confirmed during the 1+MG/B1MG face to face meeting in Brussels September 11th - 13th 2023. In short:

- The 1+MG WG8 minimal dataset for rare disease consists of the 16 agreed upon Common Data Elements (CDEs)^{35,36}
- The 1+MG WG9 minimal dataset for cancer encompasses 140 items (37 mandatory, 40 recommended and 63 optional) and is organised in eight conceptual domains for the collection of cancer-related clinical information and genomics metadata³⁷
- The 1+MG combined WG10 and WG12, with a focus Genome of Europe, have defined a very limited minimal dataset consisting of 3 mandatory items: biological sex at birth, Country of Birth and age (at time of retrieving sample for sequencing)
- The 1+MG WG11 minimal dataset for infectious diseases was still work in progress (at that time the initial version was being reviewed) and was based on COVID. describing the conceptual domains identification, Country of hospitalisation, Case status, Demographics, Comorbidities, Hospitalisation information, Infection diagnosis and Vaccination. With a total of 24 variables (concepts) and relevant accompanying value sets.

³⁵ https://eu-rd-platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/set-of-common-data-elements_en

³⁶ https://eu-rd-platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/system/files/public/CDS/EU_RD_Platform_CDS_Final.pdf

³⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.07.561259>

From the available information we created a spreadsheet with for each 1+MG WG use case a separate tab listing all concepts (individual data items) and provided value lists. Where provided or known, concepts were grouped in conceptual domains (e.g. patient, diagnosis, treatment). From those individual 1+MG use case based tabs in the spreadsheet we created a new tab named "Sunflower_union" in which we started listing all items from each 1+MG use case minimal dataset. We added two columns to provide an initial classification to a concept being an exact match or a close match to one from another 1+MG use case. Based on that initial version we created a "Sunflower_union_new" tab that grouped all related concepts from the 1+MG use cases (see snapshot shown in Figure 3) and suggested either to use one of the concepts as suggested by one or more 1+MG use cases or proposed a new one as a better fit (as shown in Figure 4). Based on consultation and discussion with the experts of the various 1+MG WGs, including experts from the European eHealth Network³⁸, as well as the GDI involved WP7 use case taskgroups, suggestions for the 1+MG Harmonised minimal data model were made (Figure 4 the dark green columns).

WG	WG_Domain/class/table	WG_Item	WG item definition	WG_proposed_Values	WG_cardinality	WG_mandatory/optional/recommended
8	2. Patient/Subject Information	Date of birth	Patient's date of birth	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)		mandatory
9	2_PATIENT	Birth_Year	Patients' year of birth as indicated on their birth certificate	Partial Date, ISO 8601 format, YYYY	1	mandatory
10_12		age (at time of retrieving sample for sequencing)				mandatory
11						
8	2. Patient/Subject Information	Sex	Patient's sex at birth	Female Male Undetermined Foetus (Unknown)		mandatory
9	2_PATIENT	Sex_at_Birth	Sex as assigned at birth	Male Female Other Unknown (a proper value is applicable but not known)	1	mandatory
10_12		biological sex at birth				mandatory
11	4. Demographics	sex at birth		0 Male 1 Female 2 Intersex -3 Prefer not to answer		mandatory

Figure 3³⁹: A snapshot of the "Sunflower_union_new" tab showing two concepts from the 4 1+MG use cases WGs. The Column WG shows the 1+MG WG number, the column WG_Domain/class/table shows if provided the domain, class or table, the column WG_Item shows the concept/item, the column "WG item definition" shows the definition belonging to the column WG_Item, the column WG_proposed_Values shows if available the Values, the column WG_cardinality shows the cardinality of

³⁸ <https://eurohealthnet.eu/>

³⁹ A landscape version of this figure is available in Annex 1

that item within the “WG_Domain/class/table” (i.e. it specifies how many instances of that one entity can occur into that domain/class/table), and finally the column WG_mandatory/optional/recommended showing if the listed WG_item is mandatory (“MUST” be provided), optional (“COULD” be provided) or recommended (“SHOULD” be provided).

WG_mandatory/optional/recommended	Suggested_Union_Domain/class/table	Suggested_Union_Item	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Definition	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Values	Suggested_Union_Proposed_cardinality	Suggested_Union_mandatory/recommended/optional	Part of sunflower:	Link to terminology/ontology that defines item	Link to terminology/ontology that defines value(s)/value list(s)	Reasoning/explanation/evidence of/suggestion	Concept: Exact match with	Concept: close match with	Example data (completely synthetic)
mandatory	Patient or Subject	Birth Date	The calendar date on which a person was born.	Complete date, without time, following the ISO 8601. If only year or year-month is available, use that.	1..1	mandatory	core	https://ncit.nci.nih.gov/ncitbrowser/ConceptReport.jsp?dictionary=NCI_Thesaurus&ncit=ncit&code=C28815		Defined in eHN: A.1.1.4:			2001-01-05
mandatory													
mandatory													
mandatory	Patient or Subject	Administrative Gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	HL7 Administrative Gender	1..1	mandatory	core	http://hl7.org/fhir/administrative-gender	http://hl7.org/fhir/ValueSet/administrative-gender	Defined in eHN: A.1.1.5 Note: This field must contain a recognised valid value for “administrative gender”. If different, “physiological gender” should be included and taken up as separate value ² communicated elsewhere.			<pre><system value="http://hl7.org/fhir/administrative-gender"> <code value="female"> <display value="Female"></pre>
mandatory													
mandatory													
mandatory													
	Patient or Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecular proven		0..1	optional	core						For now part of core but optional, since it is not a required item in any of the current confirmed minimal datasets of any use case

Figure 4⁴⁰: A snapshot of the “Sunflower_union_new” tab showing three suggested concepts for the harmonised minimal data model. Two suggestions for harmonising the existing ones as shown in Figure 3 (“birth” and “sex”; the “dark green columns” of Figure 4 are to the right side of the “Dark blue columns” of Figure 3) and one newly suggested “optional” item “biological sex at birth”. The 1+MG WG_item (“biological) Sex (at birth)” has been split into two items based on extensive consultation and discussions with the experts from the 1+MG WGs and GDI task groups involved. The experts from within the 1+MG WG3 that also are involved in the European eHealth Network made the strong point to use “administrative gender” instead of “Sex” since that item has an almost 100% coverage in all Electronic Health Records (EHRs) while the “biological sex at birth” is not always provided unless a molecular test or sequencing has been performed, hence the “Suggested_union optional” value.

The initial work on this “Sunflower_union_new” spreadsheet on the one hand was a great team effort, but on the other hand a very cumbersome process due to so many experts making new annotations as well as at the same time reviewing each other’s annotations causing lack of oversight and control. We therefore collectively changed the process and method of working. On the one hand we decided to split the “Sunflower_union_new” tab into smaller manageable separated spreadsheets. On the other hand we set up a dedicated small team, called the 1+MG Harmonised Minimal Datamodel team. The 1+MG HMD-team was assigned the preparations for each monthly meeting, being it

⁴⁰A landscape version of this figure is available in Annex 1

creating a new spreadsheet with one or more harmonised **classes** (from hereon forward we will use the term **class**, representing domain/class/table), or processing the review results from a previous monthly meeting or doing both if time allowed.

The following classes have initially been created, extensively reviewed and in the end approved and published as part of the 1+MG HMD v1.0:

- Subject
- Diagnosis
- Sample
- Sequence
- Treatment
- Environmental Exposure
- Biomarker

The classes listed do not exist on their own within the 1+MG HMD but have relations between them. The relations between the individual classes are captured in a UML-diagram⁴¹ (part of this diagram is shown in Figure 5).

⁴¹ https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/assets/minimal-metadata-model/GDI_diagram.pdf

Figure 5: Small part of the UML diagram of the 1_MG HMD v1.0 (full version available at the 1+MG framework⁴²). In red are mandatory classes, in green optional classes. The arrows with annotations like 0..1 and 1..* denote the cardinality between two classes (e.g. the arrow with 1..* between Subject class and Sample class denote that there must be at least one sample per subject)

Next we started writing technical documentation using the ReSpec documentation specifications⁴³. ReSpec makes it easier to write technical documents. It was originally designed for writing W3C specifications, but we successfully used it to write the technical documentation for the 1+MG HMD v1.0⁴⁴.

⁴² Here the link to the UML diagram (created pull request dd 2025-12-28) at <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/data-models-ontologies>

⁴³ <https://respec.org/docs/>

⁴⁴ <https://health-ri.github.io/HarmonisedMinimalDatamodel/>

5.2. The dataset description (metadata about the dataset)

At the start of creating the 1+MG HMD the spreadsheet on the Sample class also contained the Submitter class. When Europe launched DCAT-AP v3 and soon afterwards also the first drafts of HealthDCAT-AP became available we removed the Submitter class from the Sample spreadsheet and created and continue working in a separate spreadsheet named "Metadata Submission" that was reviewed and finally published in February 2025 as part of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 (with the other classes listed in 5.1).

In March 2025 the HealthData@EU platform was officially launched as open source. The initial draft of HealthDCAT-AP as developed within the EHDS2 Pilot⁴⁵ has been migrated to the European Commission's official infrastructure where the current and authoritative version of the HealthDCAT-AP specification is made available as part of the HealthData@EU release 5 and subsequent releases⁴⁶.

Per June 2025 we started working on merging the renewed 1+MG WG11 Minimal Datamodel Infectious Diseases (MDID) into the 1+MG HMD v1.0. The 1+MG MDID is the successor of the initial 1+MG WG11 minimal data model that was based solely on COVID. It now has been broadened to cover infectious diseases in general. As a result a few items at record level that describe "the submitter" and "the collector" were introduced. This caused some confusion about "metadata about 1+MG datasets" since we have the "Metadata Submission" class that provides metadata about a dataset and we have items on submitters, collectors, etc. at the record level.

Therefore, we decided to take the "Metadata Submission" out of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 and use HealthDCAT-AP for the dataset description of 1+MG datasets onwards and publish this as a minor version 1.1 of the 1+MG HMD (december 2025).

To collect data on the submitter, collector, etc. at record level (so inside the dataset and hence part of the 1+MG HMD) we created a new "Data Provenance" class. See also paragraph 8 Next Steps.

At the workshop in Paris October 15-17 2025 two dedicated sessions were organised to present, discuss and work on 1) the harmonised dataset description (metadata) about the Genome of Europe dataset(s) (i.e. datasets needed for the Allele Frequency browser) to get the metadata of those datasets submitted and onboarded in the GDI User Portal (product of Pillar II WP4), and 2) the harmonised gVCF datasets (both structure and content; e.g. aggregation will be done using a harmonised label for each subject as "AF"+"ISO-country-2character-code"+"HL7AdministrativeGender") needed to populate the national Beacons within the GDI Allele Frequency Browser Beacon Network.

After the Paris workshop, the GDI metadata squad and the 1+MG HMD-team together with the Genome of Europa (GoE) metadata specialist organised multiple hands-on workshop-like meetings⁴⁷ to complete (example see Figure 6) a spreadsheet capturing the minimal metadata of the (to be

⁴⁵ <https://healthdcat-ap.github.io/>

⁴⁶ <https://healthdataeu.pages.code.europa.eu/healthdcat-ap/releases/release-5/>

⁴⁷ GoE Metadata task force agenda and minutes

onboarded into the GDI User Portal) GoE datasets to run the first GoE use case (i.e. the Allele Frequency Browser)⁴⁸.

Suggested_Union_Domain /class/table	Suggested Union Item	Suggested_Union_Prop osed_Definition	Range	Suggested_Union_Prop osed_cardinal ity	Suggested_Union_mandatory/recom mended/optional	Usage notes	Dummy column as example	EMC	UU	University of Tübingen, heinholz - Munch	CNRGH
dc:Dataset	dct:accessRights	Information that indicates whether the Dataset is	dct:RightsStatement http://publications.europa.eu	1..1	mandatory	The ELI (European Legislation Identifier) of the EHDS was published in March 2025 and can now be included as the applicable legislation mandating that the dataset has to be made public. For health datasets, the value must include the ELI of the EHDS Regulation. As multiple legislations may apply to the resource, the maximum cardinality is not limited.	PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC
dc:Dataset	dc:applicableLegislation	The legislation that is applicable to this resource.	eli:LegalResource	1..n	mandatory		EHDS	EHDS			EHDS
dc:Dataset	dct:conformsTo	An established standard to which the described resource conforms.	dct:Standard 3 options: - Externally governed - 1+MG compliant - 1+MG cohort	0..n	optional	If your data conforms to an established standard or specification, use this property to indicate which one.	Externally governed	Externally governed	Externally governed	Externally governed	Externally governed
dc:Dataset	dct:creator	An entity responsible for making the resource.	foaf:Agent class	1..n	mandatory	This property points to an Agent who plays the creation role of the dataset.	[see below]	Erasmus MC	Uppsala University (https://ror.org/048a87296)		Externally governed common nomenclature rule to define ?
dc:Dataset	dct:description	A free-text account of the Dataset.	rdfs:Literal	1..n	mandatory	Brief description of the dataset. This property can be repeated for including a distribution is mandatory independently of the access rights. A distribution must include information on the Health Data Access Body supporting data access.	The first dummy GoE exemplar AF-browser dataset and on	Aggregated allele frequencies from the	Aggregated allele frequencies from the		set guidelines expected for descriptions ? number of
dc:Dataset	dc:distribution	An available Distribution for the Dataset.	dc:Distribution	1..n	mandatory	Note: This property will not yet be available for a lot of participating nodes, that's why it won't yet be enforced as mandatory.	[see below]	http://erasmusmc.nl/distribution_1	Can this be the Rotterdam Study Management Team? Currently they decide on access requests.	? we don't understand what to write: can you give an example of what exactly is needed here	Is there a choice or to be defined by the node? An example would help
dc:Dataset	healthdc:hdab	Health Data Access Body supporting access to data in the Member State.	foaf:Agent class	1..1	mandatory	Note: Since the value list is still being developed, this property won't yet be enforced as mandatory.	[see below]		not sure if it's decided yet		
dc:Dataset	healthdc:healthCategory	The health category to which this dataset belongs as described in the Commission Regulation on the European Health Data Space laying down a list of categories of electronic data for secondary use, Art.51.	skos:Concept [defined list of categories]	1..n	mandatory	You can select multiple categories from the dropdown-list.	(f) human genetic, epige...	(f) human genetic, e...	(f) human genetic, e... (p) data from resasr... (k) data from popula... (q) health data from ...		(f) human genetic, ...
dc:Dataset	dct:identifier	The main identifier for the Dataset, e.g. the URI or other unique identifier in the context of the Catalogue.	rdfs:Literal	1..n	mandatory	For now, use the following format for your identifier: Project-country-(ISO-2)-institute(abbreviated)-unique number	GoE_NL_HRI_1	GoE_NL EMC_1	GoE_SE_UU_1		GoE_FR_CNRGH_1

Figure 6⁴⁹: A snapshot of the "v1.0 Metadata Submission of AF-browser datasets" tab showing the GDI metadata (HealthDCAT-AP based) items (dark green columns) of datasets to be submitted to the GDI User Portal (i.e. catalogue), and the captured (i.e. manually entered) metadata by the Genome of Europa partners (orange columns, with the first orange column containing dummy example data).

5.3. ELSI related metadata

During various workshops and discussions with the GDI consortium amongst which GDI WP7 use case tasks, GDI Pillar I during the cross Pillar meetings, as well as with the 1+MG WG2 representatives it became clear that there is a need for metadata about the conditions and restrictions that apply when data is reused, ELSI elements that are important in a data request and ELSI elements that are important when approving a request with a focus on authentication and authorization⁵⁰.

The GDI metadata squad together with WP6 organised a first workshop⁵¹ dedicated to these aspects of metadata at the beginning of 2025. During this workshop on ELSI related metadata the following user stories were looked at based on 1) the results from the 1+MG Initiative and Data Protection by Design and Default (DPbDD) workshops⁵², 2) the main findings on ELSI metadata from an 1+MG WG2

⁴⁸ [GoE_minimal_metadata_submission](#)

⁴⁹ A landscape version of this figure is available in Annex 1

⁵⁰ [Agenda workshop Data Inclusion consequences of the 1+MG Governance](#)

⁵¹ [GDI ELSI meta data workshop March 19th 2025](#)

⁵² [DPbDD_Information requirements.docx](#)

workshop back in 2023⁵³, and 3) a spreadsheet created from the results obtained from an internal ordered project by Health-RI⁵⁴:

- Publish datasets in the catalog
- Finding datasets
- Request datasets
- Analyse datasets

Like with the 1+MG WG11 MDID also with ELSI related metadata there was still confusion about aspects of ELSI at the description of the dataset versus data items at record level inside the dataset itself (as in part of codebook, i.e. the 1+MG HMD). To that end in December 2025 a dedicated meeting was scheduled between members of the metadata squad, the 1+MG HMD-team, Pillar II WP6 (data management) and representatives of the Pillar I/1+MG WG2 to address views and needs on (meta)data related to consent for data discovery⁵⁵.

5.4. Cross-walks between internationally mature standards following SSSOM

The 1+MG HMD-team has prepared additional versions of each of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 spreadsheets to work on cross-walks between various internationally mature standards for both the data items and values of the HMD following the SSSOM method. For each copy of the original 1+MG HMD v1.0 spreadsheet two tabs were created, one for the matches on the concepts (the items) and one for the matches on the Values. An example screen capture (a similar part as that of Figure 4) of the spreadsheet created for working on cross-walks for “Subject” applying the SSSOM method, is shown in Figure 7. A similar tab has been created for cross-walks for the Values.

⁵³ Main-findings-ELSI-metadata.pptx

⁵⁴ ELSI Metadata Health-RI

⁵⁵ GDI Discussion about consent

Suggested_Union_Domain/class/table	Suggested_Union_Item	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Definition	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Values	Link to terminology/ontology that defines item	Item/concept EXACT match					Item/concept CLOSE match				
					SNOMED	ICD-10	NCIT	LOINC	Other (please state the source / add more columns if needed)	SNOMED	ICD-10	NCIT	LOINC	Other (please state the source / add more columns if needed)
Subject	Administrative gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	HL7 Administrative Gender	http://hl7.org/hlir/administrative-gender		None	C83501 Administrative Gender Code			GSSO: administrative gender				Recorded sex or gender
		Match source				nowhere	HL7 & biportal			biportal				LOINC browser
		mapping_justification					semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558			semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558				semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558
		author_id												
		comment												
		confidence												
		reviewer_id												
		object_match_field												
		subject_match_field												
		mapping_date						2025-05-22		2025-05-22				2025-05-22
Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecular proven	HL7 ValueSet: Birth Sex	HL7 ValueSet: Birth Sex	42013009 Finding related to biological sex (finding)	None	C164609 Sex Genotype Code			72400001 Biological sex (property)		C124436 Sex at Birth	Recorded sex or gender	
		Match source				biportal	nowhere	NCI & EVS browser (and biportal)		biportal		NCI & EVS browser (and biportal)	LOINC browser	
		mapping_justification			semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558		semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558			semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558		semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558	semmapv/Manual/Mapping_Curation orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558	
		author_id												
		comment												
		confidence												
		reviewer_id												
		object_match_field												
		subject_match_field												
		mapping_date						2025-05-22		2025-05-22		2025-05-22		2025-05-22

Figure 7⁵⁶: Small part of the “Matches_Subject_class” spreadsheet showing where found/available in dark green columns the exact matches for the items “Administrative gender” and “biological sex at birth” as well as in mid-blue the close matches for the same two items. Also the first items from the SSSOM method, namely “mapping_justification” (i.e. manual since that was the method used by the 1+MG HMD-team), “author_id” (e.g. if available the ORCID), and “mapping_date” have been completed. NOTE that this is still a work in progress.

The same SSSOM method has been applied in three workshops (so far) working on the implementation of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 into Beacon v2⁵⁷. The work focused on identifying matches (1+MG HMD v1.0 has a match in Beacon v2), as well as identifying gaps (the 1+MG HMD v1.0 did not have any match in Beacon v2). The workshop was attended by representatives of the Beacon team (both technical and data specialists) from Pillar II, the 1+MG HMD-team, and various experts from the Pillar III WP7 use case tasks. A screen capture showing an example result of the cross-walk alignment workshop on “Subject class” is shown in Figure 8.

⁵⁶A landscape version of this figure is available in Annex 1

⁵⁷[Workshops: alignment between 1+MG HMD and Beacon data models](#)

GDI minimal data model				Beacon Model					1+MG HMD > Beacon workshop					
Suggested_Union_Domain/class/table	Suggested Union Item	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Definition	Suggested_Union_Mandatory/recommended/optional	Model	Property	Type	Priority/recommended/optional	Concept match	Comments	Status	SSSOM predicate_id	Comment	Reviewers	Workshop
Subject	Birth Date	The calendar date on which a person was born.	mandatory					no match		Agreed			Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Administrative gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	mandatory	Individuals	sex	ontology	mandatory	complete match		Different agreement	skos:relatedMatch	Gender is not represented in phenopackets nor Beacon	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1
Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecularly proven	optional	Individuals	karyotypicSex	string	optional	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch	look at the comment in the cell for optional	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1
Subject	Date_of_Last_Follow_up	Date of last follow-up, partial date with month and year	conditional					no match		Agreed			Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Country of origin	A person's descent or lineage, from a person or from a population	conditional	Individuals	geographicOrigin	ontology	optional	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch		Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Subject ID	A sequence of characters used to identify, name, or characterize a trial or study subject.	mandatory	Individuals	id	string	mandatory	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch	Subject ID would be mapped as individual ID specifically. If different cohorts have the same subject ID, both should be referring to the same individual	Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Diagnosis	Date of Diagnosis	Date at which diagnosis was made	recommended	Individuals	disease > onset	timeElement	optional	partial match	Description: Age or time at which the feature was first observed	Different agreement	skos:relatedMatch	Onset may happen at any time (when symptoms first appear), and the diagnosis can happen at any time after onset. Two different entities, not overlapped semantically, just issued	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1

Figure 8⁵⁸: Small part of the “1MG HMD to Beacon mapping working spreadsheet” tab on Subject and Diagnosis showing that for some items “no match” has been found (e.g. “Birth Date” and “Date_of_Last_Follow_up”), for most items a **complete match** (with a *skos:exactMatch*) has been found and confirmed, and for some a **partial match** (for the items shown with a *skos:relatedMatch*).

Note that the item “Birth date” is a mandatory item in the 1+MG HMD v1.0 while no match has been found in Beacon v2. This issue has been signaled as an issue for the Beacon v2 team and will be solved in the near future. Other issues with respect to “mandatory” items in 1+MG HMD v1.0 which have a “no match” in Beacon v2 have been identified and are on the backlog of the Beacon v2 team.

5.5. Initial mapping exercise between 1+MG HMD v1.0 and ERDERA RD3 (without SSSOM)

A quick and initial mapping exercise was conducted between version 1.0 of the 1+MG Harmonised Minimal Data Model (HMD) and the ERDERA extended RD3⁵⁹ data model (implemented in MOLGENIS⁶⁰) to assess alignment for future joint development. RD3 also includes a ‘catalogue’ module used for the European Data Catalogue. Overall, model similarity is high and there are no concerns for achieving interoperability. Some gaps reflect differing scopes since the RD3 model is intended for NGS sample and patient tracking for unsolved rare diseases, but others highlight areas where clarification or harmonisation would reduce barriers to adoption. Key findings are:

- Dataset level
 - Distribution: This field is not mandatory in RD3, whereas it is required in HMD, indicating a difference in enforcement of metadata completeness.

⁵⁸ A landscape version of this figure is available in Annex 1

⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/gigascience/giae058>

⁶⁰ <https://molgeniscatalogue.org>

- HDAB: The mandatory status in HMD is notable given its novelty. This could restrict data import, potentially limiting participation to countries already supporting HDAB (e.g. Finland).
- ADMS: This concept is not recognised or implemented within RD3.
- Sample and clinical information
 - Sample relations: HMD supports relations between samples, a concept not currently present in RD3. This represents a potential area for future RD3 extension.
 - TNM / cancer information: These clinical descriptors are not included in RD3.
- NGS sequencing and digital resources
 - Sequence – initial_input_file_format: The terminology is ambiguous. In practice, most listed file types (e.g. BAM/CRAM) are outputs of sequencing or analysis pipelines, making the distinction between “input” and “output” unclear.
 - Digital resource – parameters: The separation of parameters from protocol is confusing. Including parameters effectively defines a specific protocol instance rather than a generic protocol, which may reduce reusability and clarity.

5.6. Extending FAIR Genomes with HMD for GDI ontology development

The FAIR Genomes metadata schema^{61 62}, recognised as promising best practice in 1+MG and B1MG, has been extended with targeted elements from the 1+MG Harmonized Minimal Datamodel (HMD) to provide a proven platform for creating and maintaining new ontology terms. This extension enabled the introduction of new domain-specific classes such as HMD Submission (FG:0000750), Treatment (NCIT:C49236), and Biomarker (NCIT:C16342), alongside new attributes including Submitter Role (FG:0000752), Data Center (FG:0000753), and Clinical Center (FG:0000754) within the HMD Submission module. All introduced ontology terms are resolvable in RDF via the fair-genomes W3ID namespace, for instance FG:0000750⁶³. Additional fields, including institution identifiers, publication descriptions, treatment-related attributes (e.g., dose units, treatment setting, response), and biomarker classifications, were also incorporated to better capture GDI-relevant metadata. Although this extended model is not yet used in operational pipelines, it has been proven to be a valuable and flexible tool in the GDI modeling toolbox, supporting the structured evolution of ontology-driven data standards.

⁶¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01265-x>

⁶² <https://fairgenomes.org>

⁶³ https://w3id.org/fair-genomes/resource/FG_0000750

6. Results

This section summarises the major outcomes up till publication of this deliverable on the work towards Integration of genomics and phenotypic data within 1+MG and specifically the project GDI.

The major results (in chronological order) are:

1. The 1+MG WG9 MDC paper⁶⁴
2. The official publication and release of the 1+MG HMD v1.0⁶⁵
 - 2.1. The unofficial technical ReSpec⁶⁶ documentation of the 1+MG HMD v1.0⁶⁷
 - 2.2. The (un)official publication and release of the 1+MG HMD v1.1⁶⁸
3. Poster on the 1+MG WG9 MDC: Advancing federated sharing of cancer clinical and genomic data across Europe: The 1+Million Genomes Cancer Working Group Minimal Set for Cancer⁶⁹
4. The minor release of the 1+MG HMD v1.1⁷⁰ accompanied by the official release of GDI metadata version 1.1⁷¹ including a delta of v1.0 to v1.1 as suggested by NEN 7522.
5. The initial mapping between the 1+MG HMD v1.0 and the ERDERA extended RD3 data model to assess alignment for future joint development.

7. Discussion

This section summarises what has not been achieved but was foreseen up till publication of this deliverable on the work towards Integration of genomics and phenotypic data within 1+MG and specifically the project GDI

1. The inclusion/merge of the new 1+MG WG11 Minimal Datamodel for Infectious Diseases (MDID) into the next major releases v2.0 of the 1+MG HMD is close to being finished
2. The cross-walks between major internationally mature standards at
 - 2.1. Data Item and value list level (like SNOMED CT, ICD-10, LOINC)
 - 2.2. Datamodel level (like Beacon v2, Phenopackets⁷², OMOP CDM)

Major reasons for not being able to finish the inclusion/merge of the new (i.e. extension of the 1+MG WG11 MDID based on COVID only to the generic infectious disease domain) MDID was the introduction of various complicating factors amongst which:

⁶⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.10.07.561259>

⁶⁵ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/data-models-ontologies#minimal-metadata-model>

⁶⁶ <https://respec.org/docs/>

⁶⁷ <https://health-ri.github.io/HarmonisedMinimalDatamodel/>

⁶⁸ [V1.1_HarmonisedMinimalDatamodel_dataset_20260107](#)

⁶⁹ [Abstract of poster: Advancing federated sharing of cancer clinical and genomic data across Europe: The 1+Million Genomes Cancer Working Group Minimal Set for Cancer](#)

⁷⁰ [Version 1.1 Release of the 1+MG HMD](#)

⁷¹ <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure/gdi-metadata>

⁷² <http://phenopackets.org/>

- The original 1+MG HMD was solely based on one single organism: Human. The new 1+MG MDID also included the pathogen that infected the human, introducing various other organisms (e.g. virus, bacteria).
- Also the sample obtained from a human has the possibility of containing more than one relevant organism.
- The introduction of various required data items at record level related to a location as well as provenance aspects (e.g. where and who made the sample swap, who registered and who submitted the data) which required rework on the 1+MG HMD by introduction of two brand new classes: GeoLocation and DataProvenance. These two new classes also required rework of the original classes of the 1+MG HMD v1.0 (e.g. the data item "country of birth")

Major reasons for not being able to finish the foreseen and wished for cross-walks both at the data item and value list level as well as the data model level is the fast amount of still manual work and subject matter expertise needed to complete this work.

While writing this deliverable the work on merging 1+MG HMD with MDID is ongoing, and once finished the crosswalk work will be continued with special attention to getting the 1+MG HMD v1.0 into the Beacon to support the first GoE use case.

Up to now we only have provided a minor release, being v1.1 including its delta, and no checks on changes in official mappings nor deprecated items. Major reason is the still ongoing work on extending the 1+MG HMD with improved 1+MG use cases like MDID as well as new use cases like the 1+MG pharmacogenomics. Once those are released as official versions and the 1+MG HMD becomes more stable the (bi)yearly checks will be performed.

Lastly, but not per se part of this deliverable, is the full implementation of the 1+MG HMD within the ecosystem of the 1+MG initiative (i.e. how countries, health data providers, and decision-makers should adopt and implement the 1+MG HMD). In parts, the implementation is already ongoing, i.e. 1) the dataset description of 1+MG related datasets in the GDI User Portal (the dataset catalogue), and 2) the implementation of the 1+MG HMD into Beacon v2 (e.g. Genome of Europe). Datasets that are onboarded adhere to the HealthDCAT-AP released by HealthData@EU (at time of publication the GDI User Portal adheres to HealthDCAT-AP release 5). Once the implementation of the 1+MG HMD into Beacon v2 is completed users could besides finding and searching a dataset at the GDI User Portal, also start asking queries (initially predefined queries, and next step by step increasing complexity of (and more open) queries) at the GDI User Portal. Those queries are based on and/or using the data dictionary (i.e. the list of variables and values) as defined in the 1+MG HMD and will be federated within the Beacon network for providing the type of answers as described in and allowed by the future EDIC Data Governance⁷³.

⁷³ Current GDI internal document: [w 202506 - GDI_D2.4 Framework for data governance_FV.docx](#)

8. Conclusions & Impact

- WP8 has, in close collaboration with B1MG-WP3, 1+MG-WG3/WG4, B1MGplus WP4, developed and harmonised various minimal data models based on the WP7 use case demands into the 1+MH HMD v1.0.
- The 1+MG HMD v1.0 (and its successors) provides an improved semantic interoperability of genomic and medical information for the 1+MG initiative and related projects and programs.
- Strengthened alignment between infrastructure and user needs through coordinated work between Pillars II and III.
- Established a foundation, both process and model (i.e. the Sunflower model) for continuous extension of the 1+MG HMD with new use cases (e.g. pharmacogenomics) as well as improvement and management of the semantic interoperability (i.e. based on the SSSOM and Respec based technical documentation and version management via Github). Near future developments in LLMs might speed up or replace the need for manually created cross-walks, also reducing the needed "maintenance" of those cross-walks.
- The dataset description (metadata about a dataset) for the 1+MG initiative has been developed and integrated into the GDI User Portal (i.e. catalogue) and is compliant to the HealthData@EU HealthDCAT-AP. Onboarding of (real) datasets, starting with the dataset description, within the 1+MG infrastructure can now commence.

9. Next steps

Within the remaining time of the GDI project we aim to:

- Finish the merge of the 1+MG HMD with MDID, resulting in 1+MG HMD v2.0
- Contribute to the realisation of the GoE Allele Frequency-browser, and potentially next use case(s) of GoE resulting in updates of the 1+MG HMD (we expect minor releases, v2.x)
- Work on ELSI metadata as well as ELSI relevant data items at record level within the 1+MG HMD (candidate for v2.0 or v3.0)
- Start onboarding the 1+MG WG12 pharmacogenomics use case related minimal data model (candidate for v3.0 or v4.0)
- Assist in the onboarding of HealthDCAT-AP compliant dataset descriptions of 1+MG datasets, starting with Genome of Europe generated datasets.
- Continue with crosswalks:
 - SSSOM work
 - Mapping the 1+MG HMD to Beacon v2 and uploading 1+MG HMD compliant data into the Beacons featuring the possibility to from the GDI User Portal query the Beacon network loaded with datasets that are compliant to the 1+MG HMD (starting with the Allele Frequency Browser as mentioned above). The complexity of queries a user can ask at the GDI User Portal will be increased step by step, beginning with predefined queries containing a limited number of adjustable parameters
- Map (and later harmonize, merge) to ERDERA extended RD3 (minor release either 2.x or 3.x)

- Improve the lifecycle management of the 1+MG HMD:
 - The official release and version control of Respec-standard generation and publication of the 1+MG HMD
 - Together with Pillar I and the future genome EDIC work on the governance and quality control of the 1+MG HMD as well as the 1+MG HMD based datasets⁷⁴. The NEN-7522⁷⁵ (the Dutch national standard for Health Informatics — Development and maintenance of standards and systems of standards) can be used as a best practice.
 - Following the NEN 7522 we will provide deltas for each minor and/or major release. First major release will be 1+MG HMD v2.0 based on the merge with the new MDID.
- Initiating and collaborating, with a working method yet to be determined, on the further implementation and uptake of the 1+MG HMD within the member states, the health data providers as well as by the policy makers.

What we won't be able to accomplish within the remaining time of GDI is:

- Publication of an official release (new version) of the 1+MG HMD including the 1+MG WG12 pharmacogenomics minimal data model since the 1+MG WG12 is still working on their use case(s) and data-needs resulting in the minimal data model for pharmacogenomics.
- A crosswalk between all major international standards (e.g. SNOMED CT, LOINC, ICD-10 or 11) for every data item and value of the 1+MG HMD, since certain data items and/or values are not yet available across all of those standards.
- A crosswalk between all the major operational data models, since adaptations are needed at both sides (i.e. we might need to accommodate a crosswalk by annotation of the 1+MG HMD or annotation of the major operational data model (e.g. Beacon v2 needs extensions to accommodate the 1+MG HMD which needs work (funding) in collaboration with GA4GH)

⁷⁴ [W 202506 - GDI_D2.4 Framework for data governance_FV.docx](#)

⁷⁵ <https://www.nen.nl/en/nen-7522-2021-en-324054>

10. Annex 1. Landscape version of figures

WG	WG_Domain/class/table	WG_Item	WG item definition	WG_proposed_Values	WG_cardinality	WG_mandatory/optional/recommended
8	2. Patient/Subject Information	Date of birth	Patient's date of birth	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)		mandatory
9	2_PATIENT	Birth_Year	Patients' year of birth as indicated on their birth certificate	Partial Date, ISO 8601 format, YYYY	1	mandatory
10_12		age (at time of retrieving sample for sequencing)				mandatory
11						
8	2. Patient/Subject Information	Sex	Patient's sex at birth	Female Male Undetermined Foetus (Unknown)		mandatory
9	2_PATIENT	Sex_at_Birth	Sex as assigned at birth	Male Female Other Unknown (a proper value is applicable but not known)	1	mandatory
10_12		biological sex at birth				mandatory
11	4. Demographics	sex at birth		0 Male 1 Female 2 Intersex -3 Prefer not to answer		mandatory

Figure 3.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Quality	WG_mandatory/optional/recommended	Suggested_Union_Domain/class/table	Suggested_Union_Item	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Definition	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Values	Suggested_Union_Proposed_cardinality	Suggested_Union_mandatory/recommended/optional	Part of sunflower:	Link to terminology/ontology that defines item	Link to terminology/ontology that defines value(s)/value(s)	Reasoning/explanation/evidence of/for suggestion	Concept: Exact match with	Concept: close match with	Example data (completely synthetic)
	mandatory	Patient or Subject	Birth Date	The calendar date on which a person was born.	Complete date, without time, following the ISO 8601 If only year or year-month is available, use that.	1..1	mandatory	core	https://ncit.nci.nih.gov/ncitbrowser/ConceptReport.jsp?dictionary=NCI_Thesaurus&ncit=ncit&code=C688615		Defined in eHN: A.1.1.4:			2001-01-05
	mandatory													
	mandatory													
	mandatory	Patient or Subject	Administrative Gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	HL7 Administrative Gender	1..1	mandatory	core	http://hl7.org/fhir/administrative-gender	http://hl7.org/fhir/ValueSet/administrative-gender	Defined in eHN: A.1.1.5 Note: This field must contain a recognised valid value for "administrative gender". If different, "physiological gender" should be included and taken up as separate value? communicated elsewhere.		<system value="http://hl7.org/fhir/administrative-gender"> <code value="female"> <display value="Female">	
	mandatory													
	mandatory													
	mandatory											Note: WG11 valuelist contains value intersex. This valuelist completely falls within		
		Patient or Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecular proven		0..1	optional	core					For now part of core but optional, since it is not a required item in any of the current confirmed minimal datasets of any use case	

Figure 4.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Suggested_Union_Domain /class/table	Suggested Union Item	Suggested_Union_Prop osed_Definition	Range	Suggested_Union_Prop osed_cardinal ity	Suggested_Union_mandatory/recom mended/optional	Usage notes	Dummy column as example	EMC	UU	University of Tübingen, helmholtz - Munich	CNRGH
dc:Dataset	dct:accessRights	Information that indicates whether the Dataset is	dct:RightsStatement http://publications.europa.eu	1..1	mandatory		PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC	PUBLIC
dc:Dataset	dc:applicableLegislation	The legislation that is applicable to this resource.	eli:LegalResource	1..n	mandatory	The ELI (European Legislation Identifier) of the EHDS was published in March 2025 and can now be included as the applicable legislation mandating that the dataset has to be made public. For health datasets, the value must include the ELI of the EHDS Regulation . As multiple legislations may apply to the resource, the maximum cardinality is not limited.	EHDS	EHDS	non relevant since this is aggregated (non-personal) data, but would be relevant for subject-level data	EHDS	EHDS
dc:Dataset	dct:conformsTo	An established standard to which the described resource conforms.	dct:Standard 3 options: - Externally governed - 1+MG compliant - 1+MG cohort	0..n	optional	If your data conforms to an established standard or specification, use this property to indicate which one.	Externally governed	Externally governed	Externally governed		Externally governed
dc:Dataset	dct:creator	An entity responsible for making the resource.	foaf:Agent class	1..n	mandatory	This property points to an Agent who plays the creation role of the dataset.	[see below]	Erasmus MC	Uppsala University (https://ror.org/048a87296)		common nomenclature rule to define ?
dc:Dataset	dct:description	A free-text account of the Dataset.	rdfs:Literal	1..n	mandatory	Brief description of the dataset. This property can be repeated for including	The first dummy GoE exemplar AF-browser dataset and on	Aggregated allele frequencies from the	Aggregated allele frequencies from the		set guidelines expected for descriptions ? number of
dc:Dataset	dc:distribution	An available Distribution for the Dataset.	dc:Distribution	1..n	mandatory	For Health DCAT Application Profile a distribution is mandatory independently of the access rights. A distribution must include information on the Health Data Access Body supporting data access.	[see below]	http://erasmusmc.nl/distribution_1	? we don't understand what to write: can you give an example of what exactly is needed here		Is there a choice or to be defined by the node ? An example would help
dc:Dataset	healthdcap:hdab	Health Data Access Body supporting access to data in the Member State.	foaf:Agent class	1..1	mandatory	Note: This property will not yet be available for a lot of participating nodes, that's why it won't yet be enforced as mandatory.	[see below]	Can this be the Rotterdam Study Management Team? Currently they decide on access requests.	not sure if it's decided yet		
dc:Dataset	healthdcap:healthCategory	The health category to which this dataset belongs as described in the Commission Regulation on the European Health Data Space laying down a list of categories of electronic data for secondary use, Art.51.	skos:Concept [defined list of categories]	1..n	mandatory	Note: Since the value list is still being developed, this property won't yet be enforced as mandatory. You can select multiple categories from the dropdown-list.	(f) human genetic, epige...	(f) human genetic, e...	(f) human genetic, e... (p) data from resear... (k) data from popula... (q) health data from ...		(f) human genetic,...
dc:Dataset	dct:identifier	The main identifier for the Dataset, e.g. the URI or other unique identifier in the context of the Catalogue.	rdfs:Literal	1..n	mandatory	For now, use the following format for your identifier: Project-country(ISO-2)-institute(abbrevi on)-unique number	GoE_NL_HRI_1	GoE_NL_EMCC_1	GoE_SE_UU_1		GoE_FR_CNRGH_1

Figure 6.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Suggested_Union_Do main/class/table	Suggested Union Item	Suggested_Union_Pro posed_Definition	Suggested_Union_Pro posed_Values	Link to terminology/ontology that defines item	Item/concept EXACT match					Item/concept CLOSE match				
					SNOMED	ICD-10	NCIT	LOINC	Other (please state the source / add more columns if needed)	SNOMED	ICD-10	NCIT	LOINC	Other (please state the source / add more columns if needed)
Subject	Administrative gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	HL7 Administrative Gender	http://hl7.org/fhir/administrative-gender		None	C93501 Administrative Gender Code			GSSO: administrative gender				Recorded sex or gender
		Match source mapping_justification				nowhere	HL7 & bioportal semapy:ManualMapping orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558			bioportal semapy:ManualMapping orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558				LOINC browser semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558
		author_id comment confidence reviewer_id object_match_field subject_match_field mapping_date												
							2025-05-22			2025-05-22				2025-05-22
Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecular proven	HL7 ValueSet: Birth Sex	HL7 ValueSet: Birth Sex	429019009 Finding related to biological sex (finding)	None	C164609 Sex Genotype Code			734000001 Biological sex (property)		C124436 Sex at Birth	Recorded sex or gender	
		Match source			bioportal	nowhere	NCI & EVS browser (and bioportal)			bioportal		NCI & EVS browser (and bioportal)	LOINC browser	
		mapping_justification			semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558		semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558			semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558		semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558	semapy:ManualMappingCuration orcid:0000-0002-7160-5942, orcid:0000-0001-8306-0380, orcid:0009-0002-3089-9558	
		author_id comment confidence reviewer_id object_match_field subject_match_field mapping_date												
							2025-05-22			2025-05-22		2025-05-22	2025-05-22	2025-05-22

Figure 7.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

GDI minimal data model				Beacon Model						1+MG HMD > Beacon workshop				
Suggested_Union_Domain/class/table	Suggested Union Item	Suggested_Union_Proposed_Definition	Suggested_Union_mandatory/recommended/optional	Model	Property	Type	mandatory/recommended/optional	Concept match	Comments	Status	SSSOM predicate_id	Comment	Reviewers	Workshop
Subject	Birth Date	The calendar date on which a person was born.	mandatory					no match		Agreed			Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Administrative gender	The gender of a person used for administrative purposes.	mandatory	Individuals	sex	ontology	mandatory	complete match		Different agreement	skos:relatedM...	Gender is not represented in phenopackets nor Beacon	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1
Subject	biological sex at birth	The sex of a person at birth as molecular proven	optional	Individuals	karyotypicSex	string	optional	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch	look at the comment in the cell for optional	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1
Subject	Date_of_Last_Follow_up	Date of last follow-up, partial date with month and year	conditional					no match		Agreed			Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Country of origin	A person's descent or lineage, from a person or from a population	conditional	Individuals	geographicOrigin	ontology	optional	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch		Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Subject	Subject ID	A sequence of characters used to identify, name, or characterize a trial or study subject.	mandatory	Individuals	id	string	mandatory	complete match		Agreed	skos:exactMatch	Subject ID would be mapped as Individual ID specifically. If different cohorts have the same subject Id, both should be referring to the same individual	Mireia, Aldar, Milan	Session 2
Diagnosis	Date of Diagnosis	Date at which diagnosis was made	recommended	Individuals	disease > onset	timeElement	optional	partial match	Description: Age or time at which the feature was first observed	Different agreement	skos:relatedM...	Onset may happen at any time (when symptoms first appear), and the diagnosis can happen at any time after onset. Two different entities, not overlapped semantically, just linked	Marcos, Mireia, Aldar & David	Session 1

Figure 8.

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.